

THE ROLE OF NAMATAK PLANT IN FOLK MEDICINE

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Abstract. In this thesis, the family, structure, species of the "Namatak" plant, its role in medicine, its medicinal properties and functions are fully discussed. The fact that one plant is a natural medicine for many diseases. It is reported that it has its place in modern treatment.

Key words: Begger's milk, Itburun's milk, Fedchenko's milk, Kokan milk, acids, salts,

Introduction. Belongs to the rhododendrons, 1.5-3 meters tall, sometimes up to 6 meters. A thorn bush. The stem is flexible, spiny and shiny, brown-green in color. The leaves are arranged in a row. The flower can be white, red, pink, orange-red and yellow. The fruit is red and false. The fruit ripens at the end of autumn. The following types are used:

Begger's name

Itburun namatak

Fedchenko namatak

Kokan namatak.

Used part. Fruit and root. The fruit is harvested until late autumn. The content of vitamin C decreases in cold-pressed fruit. Fruits are dried in the sun or in ovens.

Chemical composition and use. Namatak fruit contains a large amount of vitamin C (up to 18%). There are P, K, B group vitamins and flavonoids, organic acids, sugar, pectin, flavoring agents, lycopene, potassium, iron, manganese, phosphorus, calcium, and magnesium salts.

Fruit seeds contain vitamin E and oils.

Namatak fruits are often used in avitaminosis diseases. Keratolin, an oil extract made from the seed oil and the soft part of the fruit, is used for burns, tropical wounds, eczema, skin diseases, X-ray burns, ulcerative colitis and other diseases.

Vitamin supplements and juice are made from some types of Namatak, vitamin C is obtained, tablets and habdori are made from its dried fruit. Ascorbin is part of many complex drugs.

The preparation of kholosas, prepared from its fruit, is used in the treatment of liver diseases. In folk medicine, tinctures and decoctions are used for gastrointestinal diseases, uterine bleeding, antipyretic, bile and diuretic. This tincture is used to rinse the gums with colds and bleeding. Namatak fruit is used to energize a person, improve metabolism, and its seeds are used as a driver for diseases of the kidneys and urinary tract. According to A. D. Turova, Namatak drugs reduce the amount of cholesterol in coronary arteriosclerosis, which is dangerous in the human body.

Useful properties of Namatak. Namatak has been consumed by our ancestors since ancient times. The useful properties of Namatak are as follows:

- ▶ Namatak contains a lot of vitamin C: 10 times more than blackcurrant, 50 times more than lemon;
- ▶ Namatak should be consumed now to prevent and treat colds and viruses that peak in autumn;
- ▶ It strengthens immunity and makes the body healthy;
- ▶ It has a good effect on the heart and blood vessel system;
- ▶ Normalizes blood pressure;
- ▶ It is also useful in anemia;
- ▶ Improves gastrointestinal function, removes harmful toxins and slags;
- ▶ Helps to lose weight;
- ▶ It is considered a means of driving bile and urine

Harmful aspects of Namatak. ✖

Namatak is not recommended for everyone. Due to the fact that it contains a lot of acids, it is not recommended for people suffering from gastritis and stomach ulcers. It is not recommended to drink tinctures made from namatak for people with low blood pressure. In addition, regular and large consumption of herbal tea can lead to non-infectious jaundice.

Conclusion. We can conclude about this plant that this plant alone is a natural remedy for a number of diseases. We only need to know the ways to use this plant correctly. Namatak the plant itself and preparations made from it can be found in pharmacies all over the country. It is our happiness that we have such a plant. Namatak is a priceless blessing. let's appreciate medicinal plants!

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